

PROBLEMS IN EDUCATION POLICY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Introduction

Education is central topic of socio-economic development and nation-building efforts in Uzbekistan. Since independence, and particularly after the 2017-2021 National Development Strategy, the government has followed prioritization of reforms to modernize the education system, expand access, and improve quality. However, despite ambitiously organized policies, systematic challenges persist to affect the effectiveness and objectivity of education. Issues can create barriers to sustainable progress, such as, unequal access between rural and urban areas, outdated pedagogical practices, underpaid teachers, and weak implementation of reforms.

Research question; What are the major problems in Uzbekistan's education policy, and how do they affect the quality and equity of education?

Methods

This study uses a policy analysis and secondary literature review approach.

1. Policy documents analyzed:

- a) Presidential Decree on Education Reform (2017-2021)
- b) National Strategy for the Development of Education until 2030
- c) OECD (2021) Education in Uzbekistan Review

2. Secondary sources: Peer-reviewed articles and reports addressing teacher training, curriculum design, access to education, and digital transformation.

3. Framework for analysis. Problems are categorized into five aspects-access, teacher quality, curriculum relevance, equity, and implementation gaps.

Results

1. Access and infrastructure

a. Although primary education is universal, disparities continue between urban and rural schools.

b. Preschool access remains limited in rural areas, despite being given prominence to early childhood education.

c. Many schools lack modern facilities, libraries, and digital resources.

2. Teacher training and professional development

a. Teacher salaries remain low, reducing motivation and professional status.

b. Training programs highlight theory but offer little practical implementation.

c. There is sparse ongoing professional development, especially in rural areas.

3. Curriculum and learning approaches

a. The curriculum remains memorization-oriented, with limited importance on critical thinking, creativity, or problem-solving.

b. Mismatch appears between school content and job market skills (digital literacy, soft skills)

c. Textbooks are sometimes outdated and inconsistently distributed.

4. Equity and inclusion

a. Children from low-income families, rural communities face disadvantages in accessing quality education.

b. Gender gaps are small in enrollment but wider in job opportunities after graduation.

c. Covid-19 pointed out a sharp digital divide, many rural students remained unable to access online learning.

5. Policy implementations and monitoring

a. Reforms are often ambitious but not fully applied due to lack of resources, bureaucracy.

b. School administrators report difficulty transforming national reforms into daily practise.

c. Higher education expansion has sharply increased enrollment, but quality assurance mechanisms do not keep pace.

Discussion

The analysis reveals that Uzbekistan's education policy struggles with a gap between policy aim and classroom reality. While reforms emphasize modernization, digitalization accomplishment is obstructed by structural issues.

a) access, quality are uneven, particularly in rural and remote regions

b) teacher motivation is diminished by low salaries and insufficient support

c) curriculum rigidity prevents students from developing skills

d) Equity challenges endure, especially in early childhood education and digital learning access

e) Policy follow-through is often unpredictable, creating unreliability for teachers and schools

Policy recommendations

1. Increase teacher salaries and provide continuous development.

2.Modernize the curriculum emphasizing problem-solving, creativity and digital literacy.

3.Expand access to early childhood education and ensure preschool opportunities equally.

4.Reduce the urban-rural divide by investing in infrastructure and technology.

5.Strengthen evaluation mechanisms to implement reforms effectively.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan's education policy has made significant advances in expanding access and launching reforms, but systemic problems persist. Addressing teacher quality, curriculum relevance, equity, and policy implementation will be essential for building an education system. Without tackling these challenges, reforms risk remaining ambitious on paper but limited in practice.

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